

THE ROLE OF ONLINE PLATFORMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP

¹Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, ²Rakhmonova Aziza Tolibovna

¹Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

²Doctoral student of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11079664>

Abstract. *Currently, the digitalization processes that are rapidly developing have an impact on all sectors of the economy. The purpose of this article is to study the factors affecting the growth of the number of female entrepreneurs in the conditions of the digital economy, to create a system of online education, to share experience and, as a result, to create favorable conditions for our women to grow their own business. The article analyzes the possibilities of the "Pomegranate" online platform, a product of the International Association of "Business Woman". The goals and objectives of the project, relevance, status and the essence of the achieved results are disclosed.*

Keywords: *female entrepreneurship, digital economy, digitization, business, online platform, gender difference, internet.*

Introduction. Today, significant changes are taking place in the world economy. One of the most important reasons for these changes is the fourth industrial revolution and the widespread use of digital technologies. According to data, in 2021, 62.5% of the world's population and 90.3% of developed countries will use the Internet. [1], All industries and activities are undergoing gradual changes based on modern technologies. In addition, the small business and private entrepreneurship sector in our country is rapidly developing in the digital economy. At the meeting of the video selector on the implementation of the digital economy and e-government in sectors and regions under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, it was emphasized that the need to digitize the areas that the population is facing the most, and to ease the burden of people [2].

Business entities operating in a new way are being formed in the transformation processes in the economy. According to economist S. Degris, this news has the following three main components [3]:

- a) development of the Internet and high-speed networks;
- b) big data formed as a result of large-scale internet platforms created for commercial purposes;
- c) modern mobile devices that allow access to the Internet anytime and anywhere - mobile phones, tablets, etc. Today, you can buy a supercomputer-powered smartphone that cost \$5 million in 1975 for \$400.

Due to the socio-economic impact of these three directions, the distances have become closer and the borders have shortened in recent years, that is, the strict division of workplace, recreation place or home is disappearing. In particular, digitalization contributes to the development of women's entrepreneurship in two ways. Firstly, women's free time is increasing on the basis of modern technologies and new inventions necessary for housework, and secondly,

Internet networks and online services (also with a flexible schedule convenient for women) make it easier to conduct business activities.

Research shows that every country can invest in its national prosperity and competitiveness by encouraging the expansion of women entrepreneurs. Today, women entrepreneurs make up one third of all active growth entrepreneurs in the world [4]. It should be noted that women's entrepreneurship is more common in developing countries than in developed countries [5]. In this study, we aimed to analyze the goals and objectives of the online platform "Anor", which forms business skills, guides them to the profession, retrains and improves their skills for women who want to start an entrepreneurial activity.

In the 21st century, many governments, including Uzbekistan, began to pay attention to gender issues. A number of programs and benefits supporting women's entrepreneurship have been launched in the country [6]. However, it can be seen from their preference for traditional activities that digitization processes do not have a significant impact on women's business activities. The study hypothesizes that the development of the digital economy can make a valuable contribution to the increase in the number of women-owned businesses.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In the past century, entrepreneurship studies have suggested that women and men are equal in business, but this view has now been proven wrong. [7] Since 1970, attention has been paid to gender aspects of entrepreneurship. In 1976, Schwartz [8] published the first scientific article on women's entrepreneurship. Later, many analytical works and political speeches were made on this topic all over the world. First of all, scientific work on the concept of a business woman [9] or to compare them with male entrepreneurs [10] was focused on, then researches about the factors affecting the initiation and successful management of entrepreneurship by women became popular. [11] In recent studies, scholars have also begun to explore the impact of the digital economy on women's entrepreneurship [12].

In Western literature, the concept of a female entrepreneur was described for the first time as a woman who runs, organizes and manages a commercial enterprise. Currently, it is deeply understood that women's entrepreneurship has a great positive effect on the economy, which is the reason for paying serious attention to this area. Women's entrepreneurship is important for individuals, communities, and countries. According to A. Abritalina, the contribution of women to the national economy in terms of job creation, economic growth and wealth accumulation is huge and no one doubts it now. In addition, countries with high levels of female entrepreneurship are more resilient to financial crises and less likely to experience economic downturns. [3] As for the concept of digitization, we observed several different descriptions of its elements. [14] In this article, we studied the possibilities of the online platform "Pomegranate" developed by the international business women's association "Tadbirkor Ayol".

Research methodology,

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results.

In recent years, significant work has been carried out to ensure the rights and interests of women, and to strengthen the family institution in all aspects. In order to effectively implement the state policy in this regard, it should be noted that a vertical system is being created that penetrates to the lowest level - neighborhood and household. In our country, a special commission will be established in order to promote women's entrepreneurship to a new level and to support

their employment [15]. Until March 2025, this commission will work in each region in the "state of emergency" mode, and will organize work on vocational training, ensuring employment and attracting women to entrepreneurship based on completely new approaches and systems.

In order to ensure the execution of special assignments, the "Business Woman" international business women's association has created an online platform for training the women of our country in entrepreneurship. Experiences of advanced foreign countries in the field as well as the legal bases of development of business activities of foreign countries with similar legislation were analyzed. The online platform includes training courses "Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship", "Starting a Business from Scratch", "Marketing", "Personnel Management", "Accounting and Taxation", "Business Management in Social Networks". This system serves to raise the standard of living of women through the development of entrepreneurship, and to create new, stable sources of income for women. The main goal of the system is to bring women's entrepreneurship to a new level. The main tool for this was the creation of an ONLINE platform, which allows women to be widely involved in business activities and is aimed at constantly improving their knowledge and skills in the field of entrepreneurship. [16]

Within the scope of the project:

A unique online platform was developed for the formation of entrepreneurial skills of women who are starting entrepreneurship, to direct them to the necessary professions, to train and retrain them, and to improve their qualifications.

Instructional manuals aimed at increasing the effectiveness of women's activities in various areas of entrepreneurship and using modern information technologies were created.

The establishment of an online platform that forms business skills, guides them to the profession, retrains and improves their skills for women who want to start an entrepreneurial activity, provides an opportunity to organize educational processes remotely.

The President of Uzbekistan set a task to train 5,000 women and girls in entrepreneurship for free, and to employ 15,000 women every year. If a UNIQUE ONLINE education system is created, an average of 60 women per month from each region, 840 women across the country, and 11,760 women and girls per year will be able to be trained in the basics of entrepreneurship free of charge. [17]

The project was promoted by the initiative of the international association of businesswomen "Tadbirkor Ayl". The project was carried out with the participation of scientists of economy, law and scientific research, responsible leading employees of the Association. There are 68 state-registered branches of the association in the regions of the country, and more than 200 business trainers and specialists are working. The association has a 30-year history and specializes in business education for women and girls. In the past period, in cooperation with local and foreign organizations, 100 million projects aimed at increasing women's economic, financial and legal knowledge were successfully implemented. In accordance with the educational programs, educational methodical manuals were developed for women who want to do business and distributed to them free of charge. As a result, 50,300 women and girls acquired entrepreneurial skills. 80 percent of them were employed. 43 thousand people managed to start their business activities. Importantly, the Association specializes in training women and girls in the basics of business and entrepreneurship.

Online platform creation plan. Figure 1.

Formation of a scientific base - provision of analytical reports, educational and methodological manuals, improvement of the efficiency of using modern information technologies, strengthening of legal and financial knowledge through online educational programs

This system serves to raise the standard of living of women through the development of

According to the statistics agency's household sample observations, as of January-December 2023,

Features of "Anor" online platform.

Unlimited number of users;

The ability to connect via the Internet from any point without being separated from production;

Teaching is carried out without a teacher - this facilitates the educational process and saves resources;

The course can be repeated until the materials are fully mastered;

At the end of each course, a test is automatically passed;

All additional materials (laws, manuals, links) in one system;

Chat with other students and association;

Informing students about any event through the platform (seminars, new courses, new laws, Association and women's entrepreneurship news);

Issuing a certificate upon successful completion of each course.

On the basis of Moodle DT, an online - platform adapted version with an individual design has been developed

The platform is being filled with the necessary materials, i.e. legal documents related to entrepreneurship, training manuals, articles, lectures.

A system usage guide has been developed for platform users and every user can read it freely

Certificate forms have been developed

As soon as possible, the Association's statute on the use of the platform will be developed

2 administrators of the online platform were trained and started working

Achieved results:

Forming a scientific base -Analytical lectures, provision of educational-methodical manuals, increasing the efficiency of using modern information technologies, strengthening legal and financial knowledge through online educational programs.

Use of modern technologies -The pandemic has shown how relevant, smart and effective the system of online work and online education is. In most developed foreign countries, such a system has been effective

Social and economic impactThe creation of an online platform will have an important social positive effect in the field of entrepreneurship development and education. Business trainings, coffee breaks, lunches, travel expenses, fees for business trainers, building rent and other organizational expenses will be saved. Women and girls will have the opportunity to learn the basics of entrepreneurship without being separated from household chores.

Commercialization Prospects –The prospects of commercialization of the project results are related to the practical implementation of the software, which allows women to receive loans from commercial banks, to develop their own business, and to receive distance education by paying a certain amount of money. will give. Other similar educational institutions can use the software.

Conclusions and suggestions

Observations show that there is a great demand for distance learning programs. It is more difficult for most of our women to learn the secrets of entrepreneurship by attending training courses in an offline manner due to housework, business duties, and livelihood worries. In addition, the experience of the whole world has shown how relevant distance education programs are. As a result of studying the courses posted on the online platform, our women want to start their own business.

They become an active member of the economy as well as achieving a steady income through self-employment. At the end of the distance e-course, the students are required to pass a test, and those who score less than 80% are given a certificate. We propose that the future forms of the online platform should be reflected in:

Video courses

Video lectures

Homes

Webinar recordings

Stimulants

Trainers

Longrids

These results show that the government needs to implement digitalization processes, including policies aimed at increasing internet speeds, in parallel with other supportive measures

aimed at promoting women's entrepreneurship. In addition, maintaining comprehensive data on women in business will help researchers in the future to conduct qualitative research on the case of Uzbekistan.

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